

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Steering Smart Farming Technology Adoption toward a Safe and Just Operating Space

Discussion paper

AUTHORS	Lucie Adenäuer (UBO) Robert Finger Madhu Khanna Till Kuhn (UBO) Hugo Storm (UBO)
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1 Steering Smart Farming Technology Adoption toward a Safe and Just 2 Operating Space

3 Lucie Adenäuer^{a,*}, Robert Finger^b, Madhu Khanna^c, Till Kuhn^a, Hugo Storm^a

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5 ^a Institute for Food and Resource Economics, University of Bonn, Meckenheimer Allee
6 174, 53115 Bonn, Germany

7 ^b Agricultural Economics and Policy Group, ETH Zurich, Sonneggstrasse 33, 8092 Zurich,
8 Switzerland

9 ^c Department of Agricultural and Consumer Economics, University of Illinois, Urbana-
10 Champaign, IL 61822, USA

11

12 *Corresponding author: lucie.adenauer@uni-bonn.de

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15 **Abstract:**

16 Smart farming is transforming agricultural systems. Innovations such as precision farming,
17 robotics, and AI-driven applications are known as agriculture's fourth revolution which
18 may provide socioeconomic, and environmental benefits. However, adoption rates remain
19 below socially desirable levels due to a lack of return relative to required risks, and costs.

20 The "Safe and Just Operating Space" (SJOS) concept extends the Planetary Boundaries
21 with socio-economic dimensions covering most UN sustainable development goals. We
22 propose the "Safe and Just Operating Space" concept as a normative framework to steer
23 regional and sector-specific policy incentives toward the most impactful technologies
24 regarding urgent socio-environmental needs. This is the first time that the SJOS concept is

25 applied to designing regional policies to induce the most impactful smart farming.
26 Proposing a new type of decision-making framework is highly relevant to policymakers,
27 researchers, and industry stakeholders interested in policies to govern novel technologies.
28 Our blueprint outlines the application, discusses the advantages and limitations, and
29 highlights the required research needs for policy implementation.

30 Four implementation steps are required to apply the SJOS concept to smart technology: 1)
31 downscaling and disaggregating environmental and socio-economic conditions to define
32 regional Safe and Just boundaries for the agricultural sector, 2) scoring the regional status
33 quo, 3) evaluating individual smart technologies in terms of the different Safe and Just
34 indicators, and 4) creating the Safe and Just synthesis to enable technology prioritization
35 and target-oriented policy action. Our framework ensures that technology deployment is
36 effective in terms of timing, location, and application, enabling the attainment of a socially
37 desirable level of technology use. Relevant initiatives for which our framework could
38 facilitate effective technology prioritization include the European Common Agricultural
39 Policy, the African Union's Digital Agricultural Strategy, the Indian government's drone
40 promotion policy, and the US Farm Bill.

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42 **Keywords:** Smart Farming, Safe and Just Operating Space, Planetary Boundaries,
43 Technology Adoption, Transformation, Normative Policy Framework

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47 **1. Introduction**

48 Smart farming technologies such as robotics, precision farming, and AI-driven applications
49 digitally collect, store, and analyze agricultural production data (Finger, 2023; Storm et al.,
50 2024). These technologies offer the potential to increase the sustainability of crop production
51 across various sustainability dimensions, such as enhanced biodiversity outcomes, soil health,
52 higher productivity, and resilience, or emission of greenhouse gases (Walter et al., 2017; Storm
53 et al., 2024; Finger, 2023; Khanna et al., 2024). Ideally, enhanced sustainability would align
54 with economic benefits for the farmers, incentivizing voluntary adoption (e.g., GPS guidance
55 systems reduce fuel consumption and soil compaction, reducing cost while improving
56 environmental outcomes) (Adenäuer et al. 2020). However, win-win situations do not always
57 emerge. Smart technologies may be considered too expensive or imply new challenges such as
58 data management (Khanna and Miao, 2021). The benefits of these technologies may not reach
59 specific groups of farmers, with small or less technology-oriented farmers at a disadvantage,
60 which enhances the digital divide. Costs, benefits, and risks of smart technologies are very
61 context-specific and thus differ across regions and sectoral levels. Voluntary adoption,
62 therefore, might not reach levels that are optimal from a societal perspective (Basso and Antle,
63 2020).

64 To exploit the full potential of emerging technologies, achieving a more productive,
65 environmentally sustainable, and equitable agriculture, we propose applying the concept of the
66 “Safe and Just Operating Space” (SJOS) (Raworth, 2017) as a normative policy tool. The
67 concept extends the widely recognized Planetary Boundaries concept (Rockström et al., 2009;
68 Steffen et al., 2015) by incorporating socio-economic dimensions aligned with the United
69 Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Sachs et al., 2024). This paper aims to: 1)

70 provide a blueprint for applying the SJOS concept to guide regional and sector-specific
71 decision-making process concerning smart farming technology adoption and usage, 2) compare
72 our proposed framework with alternative normative policy approaches, and 3) discuss
73 necessary steps to operationalize the framework effectively.

74 While existing research on smart farming technology has largely focused on explaining the
75 drivers of adoption patterns and their potential impacts, there has been limited use of normative
76 approaches to determine levels of technology use that are optimal from a societal perspective
77 and that guide policy measures such as subsidies, grants, and regulatory interventions (Khanna
78 and Miao, 2021). Its application to designing regional policies to induce the most impactful
79 smart farming has not been undertaken yet. The SJOS concept is well suited as it has been
80 applied at various scales, including national (Cole et al., 2014; Sayers and Advocacy, 2015),
81 regional (Cole et al., 2017; Dearing et al., 2014), and city levels (Raworth et al., 2020), and
82 across sectors, including sustainable agriculture intensification (Prasad et al., 2022; Fang et al.,
83 2021), and urban development (Dillman et al., 2021; Krueger et al., 2020). Recent efforts have
84 further aimed to evaluate the impacts of regional policies such as the EU agricultural policy on
85 SJOS dimensions (Müller et al., 2024; Arata et al., 2025; Aladesuru et al., 2024).

86 Our proposed SJOS-based framework provides a structured approach to selecting policy
87 interventions such as investments in research and development, digital infrastructure,
88 performance-based technology taxes or subsidies, and regulatory measures to optimize the
89 development, adoption, and utilization of the most impactful smart technologies in alignment
90 with overarching environmental and social challenges. By ensuring that technology
91 deployment is effective in terms of timing, location, and application, our approach enables the
92 attainment of an optimal level of technology use.

93 Compared to other normative approaches in policy decision-making - such as full welfare
94 analysis (Khanna and Miao, 2021), explorative scenarios (Ehlers et al., 2022), or mission-
95 oriented approaches (Mazzucato, 2023) - our proposed framework offers a compromise
96 between rather formal and more informal approaches. While the formal welfare analysis
97 provides clear quantitative insights, it requires a precise monetization of all non-market
98 dimensions, which can create a misleading sense of quantitative accuracy. In contrast, our
99 framework recognizes the numerous uncertainties while still allowing the incorporation of
100 scientific knowledge, where available, systematically. Further, it facilitates the involvement of
101 diverse stakeholders, particularly in cases where clear scientific benchmarks for Safe and Just
102 indicators and boundaries are lacking.

103 In the following, we first outline the proposed SJOS-based framework before providing a
104 blueprint for its application in smart farming. Finally, we discuss the opportunities and
105 limitations of the proposed concept in comparison to existing alternatives, highlighting the
106 required research needed to fully operationalize our approach.

107 **2. Methods**

108 The conceptual framework underlying the SJOS concept recognizes that there are planetary
109 boundaries, i.e., an “ecological ceiling” that we must not exceed. Simultaneously, there are
110 socio-economic dimensions, i.e., a “social foundation” that we should not fall short of, to allow
111 for sustainable development at humanity level (Fig. 1). The ecological ceiling and the social
112 foundation are indicated as half circles on the respective side of Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Adaptation of the SJOS concept to a region and a technology

113 Using the SJOS concept, our concept evaluates regions in terms of how they currently stand
 114 regarding Safe and Just dimensions. Performance indicators for each dimension are measured,
 115 indexed, and related to the ecological ceiling or social foundation (Fig. 1). The height of the
 116 individual dimension in comparison to the boundaries then indicates to what extent the region
 117 exceeds or falls short of them allowing for a regional evaluation (Fig. 1). This visualizes where
 118 the region needs improvement.

119 Our concept also allows us to evaluate novel technologies based on which Safe and Just
 120 dimensions each of the technologies will impact and to what extent if adopted in a region. This
 121 is indicated through inward or outward-facing arrows, which visualize not only the direction
 122 of impact but also potential trade-offs between the impacted dimensions (Fig. 1).

123 Bringing the regional and the technological evaluation together, allows us to identify to what
124 extent a specific technology will likely contribute to addressing the Safe and Just dimensions
125 that fall short of the considered Safe or Just space in a region (Fig. 1).

126 Comparing the net impact of several possible technologies then allows policymakers to identify
127 the most suited and beneficial technologies for a specific region. This allows us to make
128 normative statements about moving agricultural production towards a Safe and Just space by
129 enhancing the usage of suited technologies and, based on this, to adjust policies accordingly.
130 Additionally, it can serve as a tool to visualize and illustrate the trade-off associated with
131 promoting certain technologies, which need to be considered in the policy decision-making
132 processes when deciding on which technology to go forward with and to what extent.

133 **3. Results and Discussion**

134 To apply the SJOS concept to smart technology, four implementation steps are required: 1)
135 downscaling and disaggregating environmental and socio-economic conditions to define
136 regional Safe and Just boundaries for the agricultural sector, 2) scoring the regional status quo,
137 3) evaluating individual novel smart technologies in terms of the different Safe and Just
138 dimensions/indicators, and 4) creating the Safe and Just synthesis to enhance the adoption and
139 usage of the smart technology by farmers through deriving target-oriented policy incentives
140 (Fig. 2). All steps are case-dependent and require not only scientific evaluations but should
141 also involve stakeholders in a participatory approach.

Figure 2: Blueprint on how to apply the Safe and Just framework for smart technologies.
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143 *3.1. Downscaling and Disaggregating of SJOS*

144 Downscaling the SJOS framework to regional levels and disaggregating it among sectors
 145 requires selecting the relevant Safe and Just dimensions, defining regional boundaries for each
 146 dimension and identifying appropriate sectoral performance indicators related to those
 147 dimensions (Fig. 2). Dearing et al. (2014) provide a general discussion on this process, while
 148 Müller et al. (2024) provide a downscaling to the EU agricultural sector at regional level.
 149 For regional downscaling and sectoral disaggregating, it is important to define the appropriate
 150 regional scale at which the analysis will be conducted (e.g., field, farm, landscape, region,
 151 national) (Müller et al., 2024; Custodio et al., 2023). A guiding principle should be to align the
 152 scale of analysis with the targeted scale of policy recommendations. Another challenge is to
 153 define distribution keys between regions and sectors for example in terms of the acceptable
 154 level of emissions per sector or region. While existing research provides recommendations for

155 downscaling and disaggregating (Müller et al., 2024), it is essential to acknowledge that not all
156 Safe and Just boundaries can be set based on scientific knowledge. In many cases, the definition
157 of SJOS boundaries will be based either on existing policy targets or the consultation of
158 stakeholders and experts using participatory approaches such as living labs or workshops
159 (Cascone et al., 2024). Living labs thereby are designed to focus on the user of smart
160 technology, with stakeholders co-developing innovative solutions that then are tested in the
161 actual user context. This allows for a unique opportunity to collaborate in real-world context
162 (Cascone et al., 2024). The possibility to combine scientifically sound boundaries for some
163 dimensions, where given, with societally acceptable boundaries for other dimensions, derived
164 in a participatory approach, is a key strength of the concept. This approach then enables the
165 development of a set of Safe and Just case-study-dependent regionalized performance
166 indicators and their boundaries for the agricultural sector (Müller et al., 2024).

167 3.2. *Scoring the regional agricultural status quo*

168 The next step requires scoring the regional status quo against the regionalized, sectorial
169 boundaries (Fig. 2). Selecting appropriate data sources to perform this scoring depends on the
170 selected indicators in step 3.1 and the regional focus of the analysis. There are numerous, often
171 overlapping frameworks and sources for such indicators. Under environmental legislations
172 such as the UNFCCC and the EU Nitrates Directive, monitoring activities accumulate detailed
173 data on various indicators that can be utilized for scoring Safe boundaries. In addition, the
174 indicators underpinning the SDG goals serve as a good proxy for the performance indicators,
175 especially as also the Just dimensions are covered. Ninety-eight global UN SDG indicators are
176 collected yearly for 167 countries to calculate the SDG Index. The SDG Index thereby
177 measures the distance to achieving the 17 SDG goals (Sachs et al., 2024). Further, Müller et al.

178 (2024) find that almost all of the SJOS performance indicators are covered by at least one
179 existing agricultural-policy modelling system, such as e.g., CAPRI (Britz and Witzke, 2014),
180 FarmDyn (Britz et al., 2021) or GLOBIOM (IBF-IIASA, 2023). This provides a useful basis
181 for scoring the regional status quo and, at a later stage, for ex-ante assessments of technology
182 impacts on the SJOS.

183 3.3. *Evaluating smart technology*

184 Given that many smart farming technologies are in early research or application stages,
185 empirical evidence on their scalability and impact on a specific region's environmental, social,
186 and economic targets is limited. Therefore, evaluating their effects on Safe and Just
187 performance indicators and identifying trade-offs across affected dimensions requires
188 comprising scientific insights from various ex-ante and ex-post methods, including field
189 experiments, farm and consumer surveys, expert interviews, and modeling at farm, regional,
190 or global levels. Each approach has strengths and limitations in assessing smart technologies.
191 Field experiments collect detailed field-level data and serve as trials for novel technologies as
192 they generate small-scale and case-specific data. This method is particularly useful for
193 evaluating Safe and Just performance indicators directly linked to production processes, such
194 as resource use, labor efficiency, and greenhouse gas emissions. Upscaling these results
195 however increases uncertainties regarding the impacts and interdependencies between
196 indicators.

197 Surveys, alongside ex-ante economic experiments, can capture farmer and consumer
198 acceptance, approval, and willingness to adopt smart technologies (Blasch et al., 2022; Späti
199 et al., 2022; Pfeiffer et al, 2021). Farmer behavior significantly influences Safe and Just
200 performance indicators and technology adoption drivers can be studied through models like the

201 Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen and Madden, 1986) and the Threshold Model of Economic
202 Decision-Making (David, 1975). Surveys have shown that various structural, socio-
203 demographic, and individual farmer factors determine farmer behavior (Massfeller and Storm,
204 2024; Tzemi and Breen, 2018). Since they involve relevant stakeholders, surveys are
205 particularly relevant for assessing the impacts of smart technologies on Just indicators.
206 However, as individual behavior is analyzed, aggregated effects and potential feedback
207 mechanisms must be interpreted cautiously.

208 Expert interviews offer a nuanced understanding of smart technology adoption. Existing non-
209 monetary barriers such as rural infrastructure limitations and digital literacy among farmers are
210 highlighted (von Soest, 2023). This facilitates practical recommendations and forecasting of
211 technological impacts. However, selection biases call for methodological rigor and reflexivity
212 in the interview process (von Soest, 2023).

213 Modelling approaches allow for the generation of multiple indicators from the plant to global
214 scales, capturing potential trade-offs across Safe and Just dimensions (Britz and Witzke, 2014;
215 Britz et al., 2021; IBF-IIASA, 2023). They are particularly suitable for ex-ante assessments
216 when empirical observations of technologies are not yet available. By utilizing robust and
217 comprehensive input data, models provide valuable insights at regional and global scale, where
218 field experiments and farm surveys often face constraints. However, this strength is also a
219 limitation, as the inclusion of new smart technologies requires input data to an extent not yet
220 available. The inclusion of these technologies will reduce the robustness and increase
221 uncertainty with regards to the results.

222 More research is therefore needed to fill the data gaps and allow for a more robust inclusion of
223 smart technologies into models.

224 3.4. *Creating Safe and Just Synthesis to Enhance Adoption*

225 Combining the regional scoring with the technology assessment on the SJOS performance
226 indicators results in a regional and sectoral-specific Safe and Just Synthesis indicating how
227 smart technology impacts the regional performance indicators and results in trade-offs between
228 the Safe and Just indicators (Fig. 2). This provides the basis for regional and sectoral-specific
229 policy recommendations in terms of smart technology usage.

230 In the EU Common Agricultural Policy for instance, digitalization is a key goal to enhance
231 sustainable farming, with Member States targeting significant increases by 2030 (e.g., Austria:
232 from 1.7% to 7.7%, Greece: from 3.6% to 26.1% (European Commission, 2025)). Using case-
233 specific SJOS indicators and a smart technology catalog, each state could assess regional needs
234 and identify the most impactful technologies for environmental, economic, and social benefits.
235 Smart farming technologies promise significant environmental potential. Given that these
236 technologies are at an early stage of use, identifying research gaps with regard to their specific
237 impact on Safe and Just outcomes can guide development to leverage the full potential in a
238 timely manner. Including a broad stakeholder group in our framework is crucial, as technology
239 choices influence not only farmers but also other actors along the supply chain who both affect
240 and are affected by smart farming advancements.

241 Setting a framework for the regional policy decision-making process allows for drawing
242 normative conclusions on the potential impact of smart technology on the regional SJOS. This
243 enables the determination of the necessary political incentivization for a target-oriented
244 adoption and usage of smart technology.

245 3.5. *Opportunities and Limitations*

246 Many studies highlight and critically discuss the advantages of smart farming technology
247 (Walter et al., 2017; Storm et al., 2024; Finger, 2023; Khanna et al., 2024; Dalhaus e al., 2024),
248 yet policy measures to maximize its potential remain underexplored. Others acknowledge the
249 necessity of policy goals in digitalization but they often lack guidance on formulation and
250 implementation (Basso and Antle, 2020; Grieve et al., 2019). This paper proposes to
251 incorporate the assessment of novel smart farming technologies in the SJOS concept to assist
252 policy-decision making as a normative approach to steer policy incentives towards the most
253 impactful sustainable technologies, enhancing adoption. Our framework thereby addresses
254 shortcomings in existing approaches like formal welfare analysis, exploitative scenario
255 approaches, or mission-oriented approaches.

256 From a normative economic perspective, a theoretically sound approach for policy design is a
257 formal welfare analysis. However, it faces substantial practical challenges regarding the data
258 requirements, particularly with respect to the requirement to monetize all of the relevant
259 environmental and social outcomes (Khanna and Miao, 2021). Our blueprint circumvents this
260 issue by offering an assessment method that does not require a monetization of non-market
261 environmental or social outcomes, which is notoriously difficult.

262 Similarly, exploratory scenario analyses aim to identify gaps between policy goals and current
263 digitalization trends to assess potential impacts and policy requirements (Ehlers et al., 2022;
264 Fleming et al., 2021). While the development of scenarios is well suited to leverage
265 participatory approaches involving different types of stakeholders, it is less formal in
266 transparently and systematically incorporating existing scientific evidence, for example, of

267 Safe boundaries. Our approach, however, allows the transparent incorporation of scientific
268 knowledge, where available.

269 Mission-oriented approaches are another approach to normative policy-making that aim to
270 shape economic policy by involving citizens and creating civic excitement about the power of
271 collective innovation (Mazzucato, 2023). The approach breaks down a region's biggest
272 challenges, such as countering the impacts of global warming, into more manageable policy
273 priorities (Mazzucato, 2023). While this can be a powerful approach, it requires a singular
274 focus. Our concept, in contrast, is intended to navigate between multiples policy objectives and
275 highlights potential trade-offs. Moreover, while a mission-oriented approach requires a high
276 degree of stakeholder engagement supporting the common goal, our proposed concept provides
277 a structured method for integrating stakeholder perspectives around different social and
278 environmental dimensions.

279 While we outline clear benefits of our approach to normative policy making, the underlying
280 concept of planetary boundaries and the SJOS is not without critics (Biermann and Kim, 2020;
281 Pickering and Persson, 2020). A primary concern is defining regional agricultural boundaries
282 for its use in technology assessment. Downscaling and disaggregating boundaries requires a
283 sound scientific and political process. While this is complex, relying on existing environmental
284 policy targets, some of which are already regionally established, provides a pragmatic solution
285 as policymakers must inevitably relate these targets to sector- and region-specific reduction
286 activities, regardless of the SJOS concept.

287

288 **4. Conclusion**

289 Agricultural systems are facing their fourth revolution through the innovation and development
290 of smart farming technologies. However, due to a lack of sufficient financial returns and
291 significant associated risks, the adoption as well as the development of these technologies are
292 falling short of socially desirable levels. Therefore, to achieve these levels, we apply the SJOS
293 concept to guide the regional and sector-specific decision-making process, as the SJOS concept
294 extends planetary boundaries with socio-economic dimensions. Our framework requires
295 downscaling the boundaries, scoring the regional status quo regarding agriculture, evaluating
296 the technologies of interest, and synthesizing these.

297 Relevant initiatives for which our framework could facilitate effective technology prioritization
298 include the European Common Agricultural Policy, which provides subsidies and grants for
299 farmers using smart technologies (European Commission, 2023), and the African Union's
300 Digital Agricultural Strategy, which promotes continent-wide integration of smart farming
301 solutions (African Union, 2024). In India, the government's drone promotion policy
302 encourages the use of drones for farming (Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, 2023),
303 while in the United States, the Farm Bill supports precision agriculture and smart farming
304 advancements through uniform practice-based payment mechanisms (USDA, 2024).

305 By visualizing a region's current state regarding SJOS dimensions and combining these with
306 potential technological impacts in the synthesis, policymakers are better enabled to assess the
307 occurring technology potential and trade-offs and align incentives with regional environmental
308 and social needs. This allows for policy coherence as it supports the development of
309 sustainable, smart agricultural practices in alignment with overarching environmental and
310 social challenges.

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324 *Authors' contributions*

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329

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